

A novel test method to induce bi-axial stress states in thin-ply composites under combined longitudinal compression and transverse tension

T. Rev^{1*}, P. Paulmier², F.-X. Irisarri², F. Laurin² and M. R. Wisnom¹

¹Bristol Composites Institute (ACCIS), University of Bristol, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK

²DMAS, ONERA - Université Paris Saclay, 92322 Châtillon, France

* Corresponding author - tamas.rev@bristol.ac.uk

ONERA

University of
BRISTOL

ALUMNI
AND FRIENDS

Accurately determining the strength of composites under multi-axial loadings is still a great scientific challenge [1]. The utilization of thin-ply materials allows for suppressing undesirable damage scenarios [2,3], hence the objective of this study to develop an innovative test method using thin ply carbon/epoxy that allows for a more accurate determination of compressive strength for such materials. Understanding the interaction of different stress-components on the failure of UD materials can enhance design performance (reduce costs and product lead time) while a safer operation in service is ensured.

Identification of longitudinal compressive strength/strain at failure

- Slightly non-linear behaviour well predicted by OPFM

- Longitudinal compressive strain is directly measured $\epsilon_{yy} = \epsilon_{11}$ in 90° plies
- $X_{\epsilon_c} = -1.21\%$ (2.15%)
- Inverse identification of longitudinal compressive strength
- $X_c = -964\text{MPa}$ (2.1%)

